

About the Guide

Note: These instructions are for accessing Slack via a browser. There are also desktop and mobile apps, which may have minor differences.

Welcome to The Carpentries Slack group, a place for community members to ask questions, share resources and opportunities and more.

If you're new to Slack or simply overwhelmed by the prospect of yet another Slack group, here are some quick pointers to help you configure and use the tool that works best for you. They're in 3 key areas:

1. Configuring your account
2. Notification settings
3. Communicating with others

For more detailed information on getting started with Slack, including accessibility features, please visit [their website](#).

Any questions? Email: community@carpentries.org

Acknowledgements

This guide's content was based on the Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement's "Slack quick start guide" by Lou Woodley and Katie Pratt, which is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC BY 4.0) license.

The original guide is cited as: Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement. (2020) Slack quick start guide. Woodley and Pratt doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3763730

1. Configuring your account

Profile

When you set up your profile, there are three things to bear in mind:

- Your username – please use a name by which others can identify you. Your email address will not be visible to others.
- Your avatar—Please add a profile picture or other identifier you're comfortable with so that others can more easily associate your posts with you.
- Your time zone determines when Slack will notify you and can also help others decide whether it's a reasonable time of day to get in touch.

Status updates

Status updates can be a helpful way to let others know your availability. For example, if you're away at a conference, you may want to let others know you'll be slower to respond or absent from the group.

Remember that your status will be visible to everyone in the Slack group.

To update your status, click your name at the top left of the screen and select “update status.” You can also choose a timeframe for the “clear after” dropdown to specify when you want your status update to be removed.

You can clear a status update at any time by clicking on your name and selecting “clear status” from the dropdown menu.

2. Adjusting the volume notification settings

How to find and join channels

By default, you're automatically added to the #general channel, the shared community of practice everyone belongs to. You're also added to #welcome – and encouraged to say hello there.

There are additional channels that you may be interested in. To find them:

- Click the “+” icon to the right of the word “channels” to reveal the “browse channels” page.
- Want to join in? Simply click “Join channel” at the bottom of the page. The channel will now be listed in your left-hand sidebar.
- Click a channel name in the sidebar to load the channel in the centre pane.

Configuring your notifications

Slack offers many options for determining how and when you are informed about content and at what level of granularity.

- For the overall group
 - Click on your name at the top left of the page and select “preferences” from the dropdown
 - In the Notifications section, you have options which include:
 - Set times when you do not want to be disturbed by notifications
 - Enable desktop notifications
 - Choose to be alerted when specific keywords are mentioned
- Channel by channel
 - When you're in a channel, click the “...” icon at the top right. Choose “more” and then click “notifications.”
 - Here, you can ignore any @channel messages or mute the channel entirely.
- Following a specific thread
 - You can follow that thread if another group member posts something of particular interest.
 - Click the ellipsis (three dots) to the right of the original post and select “follow message” from the dropdown.
- Getting a reminder about a specific thread
 - You can also be reminded about a thread at a more convenient time. From the ellipsis to the right of the original post, select “remind me about

this” from the dropdown and choose a timeframe.

Muting or leaving channels

- If a channel has become too noisy, you can additionally:
 - Mute it: Click the “...” icon at the top right in a channel. Choose “more” and then choose “mute” from the dropdown.
 - Leave it: In a channel, click the “...” icon at the top right. Choose “more” and then choose “leave” from the dropdown.

3. Communicating with others

A few points of etiquette

- Use threads to continue conversations.
 - Anyone can reply directly when someone posts a brand-new item in a channel, creating a thread. Threads allow separate conversations in the group without confusion and enable members to choose which conversations to follow more closely.
 - To add a comment to a thread, click the speech bubble icon to the right of an existing post.
- Respect the context of this shared space.
 - While this group is open to anyone interested in The Carpentries, we want it to be a place where learning can happen in a supportive, safe environment.
 - Please DO NOT take conversations out of context and copy/paste them elsewhere without the permission of all the individuals who posted.
 - We are dedicated to providing a welcoming and supportive environment for all people, regardless of background or identity. By participating in this community, participants agree to abide by [The Carpentries' Code of Conduct](#) and accept the procedures by which any Code of Conduct incidents are resolved. Any form of behaviour that excludes, intimidates, or causes discomfort is a violation of the Code of Conduct.
- Not all communications will be synchronous.
 - While IM-based conversations can feel very immediate, you don't have to respond to messages immediately, nor expect others to respond immediately. We're all busy!

Sending private messages

It can be helpful to others when you share resources and brainstorm solutions to "work out loud" in a specific thread because your learning becomes a future resource for others, too.

However, sometimes you want to start a private conversation. To do this, go to the direct messages section on the bottom left of the left-hand side bar. Click the + icon to start a new message. You can add more than one recipient to create a group message.